

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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Umumiy o'rta ta'lim o'quvchilarida harakat qobiliyatlarini nazorat qilish asoslari.

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada umumiy o'rta ta'lim o'quvchilarida harakat qobiliyatlarini shakllantirish hamda harakatlar orqali jismoniy sifatlarni takomillashtirish haqida so'z yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: harakat, jismoniy sifatlari o'quvchi, ta'lim-tarbiya, chidamlilik, tezkorlik.

O'quvchi rivojlanishining irsiy dasturlari tomonidan joylashtirilgan jismoniy imkoniyatlarning tegishli yig'indisi ato etilgan bo'lib, organlar, organizm tuzilmalarining biologik yetilishi davomida shaxsiy imkoniyatlar rivojlanib, insonning har-xil jismoniy xususiyatlarini belgilaydi. Tadqiqot ma'lumotlarga ko'ra, so'nggi 20 yil mobaynida o'quvchilarning jismoniy rivojlanishida qayd etilgan umumiy ijobiy yo'nalishlar (gavdaning barcha o'lchamlari kattalashuvi) fonida ularning harakat tayyorgarligida sezilarsiz o'sish kuzatiladi, bir qator ko'rsatkichlar esa (tezkorlik, tezlik-kuch, imkoniyatlari) ancha pasayadi. Shunga qaramay, mutaxassislar, jismoniy sifatlarni tarbiyalash, maqsadli harakat amallariga o'rgatish aynan maktabgacha va boshlag'ich ta'lim davrda boshlanishi kerak, deb hisoblaydilar.

O'quvchilar va o'smirlar harakat faolligi sifat jihatlarini rivojlantirishning fiziologik omillari mushaklar hamda vegetativ organlar faoliyatining boshqarilishini takomillashtirishda namoyon bo'ladi. Qisqa muddatli, tezkorlik va kuch harakatlarida asab-mushak tizimi faoliyati boshqaruvini yaxshilashga ko'proq ahamiyat beriladi. Birmuncha uzoq muddatli faoliyatda harakat funksiyalarini takomillashtirish bilan birga vegetativ funksiyalarni muvofiqlashtirish ham jiddiy ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Biroq o'quvchilar va o'smirlar organizmining kuch, tezlik va chidamlilik ko'rsatkichlari yaxshilanishini belgilaydigan funksiyalarining fiziologik boshqarilishini yaxshilashda eng muhim o'rinni asab tizimi, ayniqsa, mushak zo'riqlashlarida organizmning funksiyalari yaxshilanishini ta'minlovchi

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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Том 2, Выпуск 9, 30 Сентябрь

aloqalarning shaklanishi egallaydi. Shunday qilib, o'quvchilik davrida kuch, tezlik va chidamlilikning o'zaro aloqadorligiga oid turli-tuman shakllarni belgilovchi fiziologik mexanizmlar ham xilma-xildir. Shartli-reflektor omillar muhim ahamiyatga ega. Mashg'ulotlar davomida biror yo'nalishdagi kuch, tezlik yoki chidamlilikni rivojlantiruvchi harakatlar uchun markaziy asab tizimida mushaklar hamda vegetativ organlar ishini dasturlashtirishning ma'lum shakllari yuzaga keladi. Olimlar fikricha, o'quvchi hayotining oltinchi yili kuchni, jumladan, tezlikkuch qobiliyatlari hamda harakatlar tezkorligini tarbiyalashning sensitiv davri hisoblanadi. Olti yoshda mazkur sifatlarni shiddat bilan rivojlantirish qobiliyati saqlanib qoladi va umumiy chidamlilikni tarbiyalash imkoniyatlari paydo bo'ladi. 5-6 yoshli o'quvchilarda kuch, chidamlilik, egiluvchanlik, makonda maqsadida mo'ljal olish qobiliyatlari) bo'yicha yetti yoshli o'g'il o'quvchilar shu yoshdagi qizlardan o'zib keta boshlaydi. Biroq harakatlarni muvofiqlash qobiliyatlarining ko'pgina ko'rsatkichlari bo'yicha o'g'il o'quvchilarning yaqqol ustunligi faqat 13-14 yoshlarga kelib ko'zga tashlanadi.

B.M. Zuyev tadqiqotlarida qo'lga kiritgan ma'lumotlar muallifga turli jinsli o'quvchilarda asosiy o'lchamlari bo'yicha harakatlar aniqligining notekis va har xil muddatli rivojlanishi bilan tavsiflanishi haqida xulosa chiqarish imkonini beradi. Tajriba qizlarning besh va olti yoshlarda, o'g'il o'quvchilarning esa yetti yoshga kelib makoniy aniqlikqa oid topshiriqlarni bajarishda ustunroq ekanligini ko'rsatdi. Besh va olti yoshga o'tgan o'g'il o'quvchilarda harakatning vaqt o'lchamini takrorlash aniqligi o'quvchi qizlarnikiga nisbatan yuqoriroq, yetti yoshli o'g'il o'quvchilar esa tengdosh qizlarga nisbatan topshiriqni yomonroq uddaladilar. Qizlarning barcha yosh guruhlarida harakatning dinamik xususiyatini takrorlash aniqligi o'g'il o'quvchilardagiga karaganda yuqoriroq. Umumiy o'rta ta'lim davrida jismoniy sifatlarning rivojlanish dinamikasiga xos jinsiy tafovutlarni qayd etar ekanlar, olimlar mazkur tafovutlarning kattaliklari hamda ishonchliligi xususidagi savolga uzil-kesil javob bermaydilar. Ayrim tadqiqotchilar asosiy harakat sifatlarining rivojlanish darajasi bobida o'g'il o'quvchilarning qizlarga nisbatan ustunligi haqida fikr yuritib, o'quvchilarga jismoniy tarbiya jarayonida tabaqalashtirib yondashish zarurligini ta'kidlaydilar. Boshqalari yetti yoshgacha o'g'il o'quvchilar va qizlarning jismoniy sifatlari rivojlanish darajasidagi farq u qadar jiddiy emas, uni jismoniy tarbiya

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 9, 30 Сентябрь

vositalarini tanlashda e'tiborga olish shart emas, deb hisoblaydilar va o'quvchilar jismoniy tarbiyasiga ularning jinsidan kelib chiqib turlicha yondashish maqsadga muvofiqligini ko'rsatadilar.

Ko'pgina mualliflar maktab yoshdagi o'quvchilarda alohida harakat sifatlarining namoyon bo'lish darajasida muayyan ritm mavjudligini aniqlaganlar. Harakatlarning eng yuqori darajadagi muvofiqligi kunduz kuni kuzatilgan. Mushaklarning ishchanlik qobiliyati bahorda orta borib iyunda maksimal qiymatgacha yetadi, ayni vaqtda jismoniy rivojlanish sur'atlari ham tezlashadi.

Bunday qonuniyat Rossiyaning barcha iqlimiy mintaqalari uchun xosdir. Olimlar noqulay iqlim sharoitlari o'quvchilarning jismoniy sifatlari rivojlanishiga salbiy tasir ko'rsatishini qayd etadilar. O'quvchilarning alohida harakat qobiliyatlari rivojiga sensitiv davrlarni e'tiborga olgan holda aksentli ta'sir ko'rsatishning ulkan imkoniyatlari tajriba yordamida tasdiqlangan. Bu qobiliyatlar shu yosh uchun yetakchi jismoniy sifatlarni rivojlantirishga qaratilgan bo'lib, ular faqat darajani ko'tarishgagina imkon bermay, boshqalarining to'laqonli, har tomonlama shakllanishini ta'minlaydi. Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarda chidamlilikni tarbiyalashda jismoniy yuklamalarning tuzilishini tatbiq etar ekan, olti yoshda bir tomondan chidamlilik bilan jismoniy ishchanlik qobiliyati orasida, ikkinchi tomondan tezkorlik, tezlikkuch sifatleri va chaqqonlik orasida aloqadorlik hamda o'zaro bir-birini taqozo etish munosabatlari mavjud ekanligini, ular ko'p hollarda juda ahamiyatli ekanligini aniqladi. Buni, ehtimol, alohida harakat qobiliyatlarining rivojlanish jarayonidagi o'zaro aloqadorligi asosida yotuvchi turli mashqlar va harakatlarni bajarish vaqtida ro'y beradigan inson organizmidagi o'zgarishlar umumiyliigi bilan tushuntirish mumkindir.

Yetti yoshga kelib, jismoniy qobiliyatlarning rivojlanishida miqdorning va aloqadorlik darajasining kamayishiga moyillik kuzatiladi. Kuch, tezkorlik, chidamlilik, chaqqonlikni faol rivojlantirishni bu davrda jismoniy tarbiya jarayonidagi eng muhim maqsadlardan biri deb hisoblaydilar, chunki mazkur yosh davrida o'quvchilar endi murakkab harakat faoliyatlarini bajara oladilar. Asosiy harakat turlari bo'yicha ko'nikmalarning shakllanish tezligi va mustahkamligi eng avvalo jismoniy sifatlarning rivojlanish darajasiga bog'liqdir. Shuningdek, jismoniy tarbiya bilan shug'ullanmaydigan maktab o'quvchilarda harakat sifatleri ko'rsatkichlariga irsiy ta'sirotlar o'lchami xuddi tananing barcha

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 9, 30 Сентябрь

darajasini bevosita testlash noaniq natija beradi, chunki bu natija mazkur sifatning mavjud imkoniyatlari bilan bog‘liqmi, yoki uning yoshga bog‘liq holda shakllanish sur‘atlari – tezlashgan yohud sekinlashgan sur‘atiga xos xususiyatlargami, aniq emas . Adabiyotlarda maktabgacha umumta‘lim maktablarning boshlag‘ich ta‘lim davrida harakat amallariga o‘rgatish va jismoniy sifatlarni majmualari rivojlantirish bo‘yicha yetarli miqdordagi tadqiqotlar mavjud emas.

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МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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Том 2, Выпуск 9, 30 Сентябрь

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МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

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- 42.

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

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